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SOCLIMPACT

**Downscaling climate impacts and decarbonisation pathways
in EU Islands, and enhancing socioeconomic and non-market
evaluation of Climate Change for Europe, for 2050 and beyond**

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**Work Package 4:
Modelling climate shocks and biophysical impacts**

Deliverable 4.4b

Report on storm surge levels for different scenarios and different time horizon

Coordinated by ENEA with the participation of all WP4 partners and reviewed by Salvador Suárez García (ITC), according to the quality review internal process.

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1. Introduction

Extreme sea water levels (ESL) arising from the superposition of waves, surge and projected sea level rise constitute a threat for the coastal environment and economies, and coastal managers are facing the necessity of assessing the associated risks across a range of spatial and temporal scales that demand complex and differentiated approaches. Comprehensive regional-scale projections of ESL for the European shoreline have recently emerged (Vousdoukas et al., 2017), which, albeit inadequate for the design of specific measures, can nevertheless help highlight vulnerabilities and emerging research issues, such as the difficulty in accounting for the cascading effects from sea-level rise to effective coastal impacts, such as increased wave run-up, erosion and beach loss (Thiéblemont et al., 2019). In addition, regional-scale assessments could contribute to increase risk perception among policy makers and citizens, thus prompting the development and adoption of suitable adaptation and risk-aversion plans.

This Report summarizes the results obtained in the SOCLIMPACT Project that quantify coastal hazard components for selected European islands, which might be more exposed and less resilient with respect to the mainland, and reports a zero-order evaluation of some cascading effects of sea level rise that are transversal to several economic sectors, in particular tourism and maritime transport.

2. Components of extreme sea water levels

Surge

Storm surge is an abnormal rise of water generated by a storm, over and above the predicted astronomical tides, generated by a cyclone moving toward the coast. The rise in water level can cause extreme flooding in coastal areas, particularly when storm surge coincides with the periodic high tide. While the storm intensity contributes to the overall storm surge level, this is also dependent on forward speed, central pressure, and angle of approach (relative to the coast) of the storm, as well as on the local topography and bathymetry. In particular, the latter determine the relative weight of the wind and pressure components of the storm surge: the strong cyclonic winds push water toward the shore, causing higher water levels ahead of the advancing storm (wind set-up); at the same time, an increase in water level is induced by the lower atmospheric pressure in the storm interior, and a surface bulge occurs within the storm, highest at the storm's center and decreasing at the storm's periphery (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1 – Schematic graphic representation of water pile-up originated by wind and atmospheric pressure (from: <https://www.nhc.noaa.gov/surge>)

Mediterranean Sea

Surge level estimates for the Mediterranean Sea have been derived from the set of numerical simulations performed with the Hydrostatic Padua Sea Elevation Model (HYPSE) already described in D4.2 (Conte and Lionello, 2013, Lionello et al. 2017).

RCP4.5 – SURGE LEVELS

Fig. 2 – Surge levels as predicted by the HYPSE Model: Ensemble Mean (left) and the associated Ensemble STD (right) for the historical reference period (top), RCP4.5 time mid-century window (centre) and RCP4.5 end-of-century time window (bottom).

Here we present basin-wide results showing that climate change does not appear to have a major impact on surge levels for either RCP4.5 or RCP8.5, in correspondence of the islands considered in SOCLIMPACT (Figs. 2 and 3 – the reference period field is shown in the top left panel). In addition, only a few centimetres separate the ensemble max from the ensemble mean (Figs. 4 and 5). The ensemble standard deviation is generally low (around 10% of the modelled levels or lower).

RCP8.5 – SURGE LEVELS

Fig. 3 – Surge levels as predicted by the HYPSE Model: Ensemble Mean (left) and the associated Ensemble STD (right) for the historical reference period (top), RCP8.5 time mid-century window (centre) and RCP4.5 end-of-century time window (bottom).

The mean surge contribution to high water levels can be assumed to be approximately 25 cm for all the islands except Cyprus, where it increases to about 30 cm, while the maximum impact is roughly 5 cm higher.

RCP4.5 – SURGE LEVEL MAX

Fig. 4 – Maximum surge levels as predicted by the HYPSE Model: Ensemble Mean (left) and the associated Ensemble STD (right) for the historical reference period (top), RCP4.5 time mid-century window (centre) and RCP4.5 end-of-century time window (bottom).

RCP8.5 – SURGE LEVEL MAX

Fig. 5– Maximum surge levels as predicted by the HYPSE Model: Ensemble Mean (left) and the associated Ensemble STD (right) for the historical reference period (top), RCP8.5 time mid-century window (centre) and RCP4.5 end-of-century time window (bottom).

North Atlantic Sea

Storm surge in the North Atlantic Ocean is the main driver of severe coastal flooding, with tropical cyclones causing the most extreme events. However, extra-tropical storms can also give rise to hazardous sea levels, especially when with coinciding with high tide (Needham et al., 2015; Pugh, 1987). Such events have been extensively recorded along the US coastline and in the Caribbean region (<https://www.nhc.noaa.gov>, <http://surge.srcc.lsu.edu/data.html>, <https://stormcarib.com/climatology/>), although a database of storm surge levels is not available for the latter region, whose islands are the first to be encountered along the trajectories of hurricanes that originate off the west coast of Africa, and then travel across the warm waters of the tropical Atlantic Ocean, consistently gaining strength. For this reason, the area is exposed to extremely severe winds and waves. In order to improve coastal hazard impacts, Krien et al., 2017 performed a set of synthetic numerical experiments to investigate the statistical

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distribution of such events in Martinique, and provided result for the combined effects of storm surge and waves. They showed that wave setup has a major role in determining high water levels, while the narrow island shelf limits the piling-up of wind-driven water on the shoreline. Tides were neglected due to their low amplitude (less than 35 cm).

Data of storm frequency for the Azores have been derived from historical documentary records (Andrade et al., 2008). Cyclones crossing this area include tropical cyclones that reach the U.S. coast, gaining strength as they travel on, as well as subtropical cyclones that curve pole-ward in the mid-Atlantic very early in their development and then lean eastward, affecting the Azores Islands and giving rise to storms of very variable intensity (Gomes et al., 2018, <https://coast.noaa.gov/hurricanes/#map=4/32/-80>). Moreover, beside being exposed to the impact of cyclones travelling across the Atlantic Ocean, the Azores are also affected by the periodic shifting of the storm tracks towards lower latitudes, which induces an increase in the sea level related to the inverse barometer effect (Cid et al, 2015). Return levels between 20 cm and 40 cm have been reported in the literature, for return times ranging from 1 to 100 years (Fernandez Montblanc et al., 2019).

On the contrary, the Canary Islands do not lie on the typical trajectories of cyclones and therefore appear to be more sheltered from extreme weather, although they can be occasionally in the path of cyclones crossing the Atlantic (U.S. Weather Bureau, 1942, Quitián Hernández et al., 2016). Here, a surge forecast model has been implemented, showing that residual sea surface elevation (i.e. the difference between measured sea level and tide) is mainly induced by the atmospheric pressure field and does not exceed a maximum of about 20 cm, while the wind contribution is negligible due to the narrow continental shelf, although it can be relevant during severe storms (Alvarez et al., 2001). Recently, a global reanalysis based on the Delft3D software has been released (Muis et al., 2016), that provides time series of tides and surges, and estimates of extreme sea levels, complementing already existing modelled data sets, both global (Vafeidis et al., 2008) and regional (e.g. Kernkamp et al., 2011, Cid et al., 2014). A hind-cast simulation has also been performed and validated (Fernandez et al., 2019). However, while validation statistics and extreme return levels are easily accessible, raw data of surge level time series are not directly available.

Mean Sea Level

Mean Sea Level projection maps for the islands of interest have been presented in D4.3, which constitutes the reference for the methods used and the results obtained. The corresponding mean values for each island are reported in Table 1, for RCP4.5 and RCP8.5, while individual maps also including the high-end and low-end projections, representative of the ensemble spread, are included in the Annex to this Report. Results for the Atlantic Islands rely on CMIP5 global projections ($1^{\circ}\times 1^{\circ}$ spatial resolution), and take into account the oceanographic circulation, the thermo-steric component and the ocean mass increase due to continental ice melting, as well as gravitational and viscoelastic deformations (originating from continental ice melting and changes in land water reservoirs) and the regional pattern of the Glacial Isostatic Adjustment (GIA), which were obtained from independent gravitational and viscoelastic models. For the Mediterranean, local differences with respect to the sea level in the North-Eastern Atlantic were computed from the higher resolution regional oceanographic experiments performed within the MED-Cordex programme, which account for the sea level drop across the Gibraltar Strait. As regional simulations do not include the atmospheric pressure loading, the latter was estimated from Regional Barotropic Models (RBMs). It

must be noted that the use of regional models constitutes an improvement with respect to even very recent approaches that, on recognition that global models are inadequate for the assessment of regional sea-level in marginal seas, yet constrain the Mediterranean stereodynamic sea-level projections to those of the Atlantic in proximity of the Gibraltar Strait, the entry point to the Mediterranean Sea (Thiéblemont et al., 2019).

Island	RCP4.5 2046-2065	RCP8.5 2046-2065	RCP4.5 2081-2100	RCP8.5 2081-2100
Balearic	25	33	50	66
Canary	27	37	55	74
Crete	23	32	46	63
Madeira	27	37	55	75
Sardinia	22	30	44	60
West	27	35	54	70
Azores	24	34	49	69
Baltic	20	28	40	57
Corsica	21	29	43	58
Cyprus	20	29	41	58
Malta	24	32	48	65
Sicily	23	31	46	63

Table 1 - Projected sea level rise (cm) with respect to the present (1986-2005) values for the different islands and two time horizons, the near future (2046-2065) and the far future (2080-2100) under scenarios RCP4.5 and RCP8.5.

Waves

Wave climatology has been already presented in D4.3. Here, in order to contribute to an overall assessment of Extreme Sea Level (ESL) for the island of interest and the Mediterranean coast (see section “Concurring effects of SLR and waves), the return levels corresponding to 20-, 10- and 5-year return times have been computed (Fig. 9 and Figs. 16-20 – leftmost label-bar). Individual maps for the islands are included in the Annex to this Report. Such reference return levels represent less probable, yet definitely possible, events that should be accounted for in the decision-making process. Their return times were selected as the longest compatible with the time-slices considered in this study (i.e. 5, 10 and 20 years for the Mediterranean and 5 and 10 years for the Atlantic Sea). Albeit being too short to support the design of “hard” adaptation measures, whose life span is expected to be several decades long in order to guarantee cost-effectiveness, such return times can nevertheless be relevant to evaluate the return-on-investment of “soft” measures or of mid-term exploitation of coastal infrastructures (e.g. beach resorts). It must be noted, however, that the probability of having at least one event exceeding the return level associated with a N-year return period during a N-year time window (highlighted in red in Table 2) is anyway greater than that of its complement (no events exceeding the limit in the N-year time window), and that the return level cannot be considered a “no-risk” safety level in evaluating the survivability and sustainability of structures or plants.

Return Period [years]	Probability of occurrence				
	1 years	2 years	5 years	10 years	20 years
5	20%	36%	67%	89%	99%
10	10%	19%	41%	65%	88%
20	5%	10%	23%	40%	64%

Table 2 – Probability of occurrence of at least one event exceeding the return level associated with a given return period (blue) in a given time window (green), according to the formula

$$R_{L,T} = 1 - (1 - 1/T)^L$$

where L=length of time window, T=Return Period.

Mediterranean Sea

The available numerical experiments, forced by different atmospheric models, were not pooled together in order to allow considering a worst-case scenario, as differences arising from discrepancies in the forcing wind fields are apparent. Although caution is necessary in driving clear-cut conclusions from the results shown (Figs. 16-20 - leftmost colour-bar), due to the limited statistical representativeness of the sample, the agreement between models in projecting moderate climate-change induced variations in the wave field, generally in the direction of a decrease in wave heights, allow to regard this as a fairly robust outcome, in line with scientific literature (Vousdoukas et al., 2017)

North Atlantic Sea

In addition to the high resolution simulations already presented in D4.2 and D4.3, new numerical experiments were performed with the WaveWatch III model, in view of the particular sensitivity of Atlantic islands to the climate-change induced dislocation of the tropical and sub-tropical zonal belts, and of the documented inability of state-of-the-art General Circulation Models to satisfactorily represent the relevant processes that govern the atmospheric circulation in these regions (Byrne et al., 2018). Therefore, a second set of projections was obtained by forcing WaveWatch III with the wind fields from the Australian Community Climate and Earth System Simulator coupled model (ACCESS-CM), to complement the preliminary results obtained by using the Hadley Centre global model as a driver (Figs. 7 and 8). The choice of the global driver and the experiment set-up was dictated by the availability of the spectral boundary conditions. Return levels corresponding to 10- and 5-year return times for the North Atlantic and the reference period are shown in Fig. 9, while maps for the individual islands are included in the Annex to this Report for both the reference period and the scenarios. The monthly climatological means of the two different forcing wind-fields (reference period 1986-2005) are shown below for August and September, when cyclone and hurricane activity is highest (<https://www.nhc.noaa.gov>), and for January, when the winter swells from the North Atlantic hit the Azores.

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Fig. 7 - WaveWatch III wind forcing field - Climatological Monthly mean for September: Hadley Centre Model (top) and ACCESS-CM (bottom)

Fig. 8 – WaveWatch III wind forcing field – Climatological Monthly mean for January: Hadley Centre Model (top) and ACCESS-CM (bottom)

Significant differences in both intensity and direction are apparent, which cannot but be reflected in the projected wave fields for the North Atlantic and in the derived return levels (Fig. 9). As a matter of fact, the ability of the CMIP5 global models to correctly represent the dynamics across the equatorial and tropical belts, and the number, intensity and trajectories of tropical and extra-tropical cyclones (also related to spatial resolution) has been found to be affected by systematic biases, generally attributable to both insufficient resolution and model deficiencies (Zappa et al., 2013, Byrne et al., 2018). Therefore, although results for the Atlantic Islands are included in the Annex to this Report, discrepancies between the two sets of wave simulations conducted within

Fig. 9 – Reference period: Wave heights for return times equal to 10 and 5 years (from top to bottom). Left: HADLEY; right: ACCESS-CM.

SOCLIMPACT do not allow to derive any conclusive indication as to the intensity and frequency of extreme events, in particular if the objective is to define a robust framework for risk assessment.

Concurrent effects of MSL and waves

Future extreme sea levels (ESLs) and flood risk along European coasts will be strongly impacted by global warming, affecting all its components (i.e. storm surge, mean sea level and wave height). Due to the lack of storm surge data for the Atlantic Island, here projections for the extreme levels arising from the concurrent effect of relative sea level rise and wave height only are presented. The additional surge contribution can be then added for the Mediterranean islands of interest for SOCLIMPACT (approximately 30-35). cm).

Results are shown for both the significant wave height, assumed to be a first rough estimate of wave run-up, and for the fraction that can be regarded as a reasonable estimate of wave setup. Although results that were derived for the open ocean cannot be easily extrapolated to the coastal regions, and approximate methodologies cannot possibly substitute the dedicated, high resolution monitoring and modelling of complex coastal processes (Klingbeil et al., 2018), yet the need to provide reliable assessments of wave-induced hazards at large spatial scales (regional to global) has prompted the development of a variety of approximate empirical methods that link on-shore effects to the offshore wave heights (for a review, see Dodet et al., 2019). The discrepancy between setup or run-up predicted by empirical formulas and those observed can be substantial, due to second order processes that are not represented by the selected predictors, to the insufficient length of the observational time series used for the calibration and/or validation, to the limited range of their applicability, to their having been mainly derived for sandy beaches. Nevertheless, empirical formulas provide zero-order estimates that can guide further monitoring and modelling efforts and increase coastal managers' awareness, by at least giving a hint of the magnitude of the climate-change related threats.

Wave setup

Incident wave break on beaches before they uprush on the foreshore slope. The time-varying maximum shoreline elevation above the still water level is defined as *run-up*, separated into *wave setup* (the mean elevation above water level) and *swash* (fluctuations about the setup level). A schematic representation of the process is shown in Fig.10. These wave-induced processes are of major importance for coastal management as they can significantly enhance coastal flooding and erosion.

For regular waves breaking on smooth, uniform surfaces, the ratio between wave setup

Fig. 10 – Schematic representation of wave setup and wave run-up

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and wave significant height is on the order of 0.2, an approximation that has been widely used in coastal engineering since its first derivation (Bowen et al., 1968, Holman, 1986), and that used to derive the figures presented in this Report and in its Annex. On the contrary, wave run-up is usually taken to be proportional to the surf similarity parameter (see the following dedicated section), which decreases with slope. As a result, wave energy can be assumed to be almost completely dissipated for regular waves breaking on gentle slopes, where setup dominates and linear approximations are better applicable, while the dominant swash determines non-negligible wave reflection on steep slopes. The results presented in this Report therefore only constitute a first approximation of wave impacts on gently sloping sandy beaches, and should not be generalized beyond their range of applicability. In order to provide an estimate of future impacts potentially associated with wave breaking, label-bars were added in the figures that account for the basin-averaged sea level rise with respect to present conditions, which is so far considered the main contributor to coastal hazards in Southern Europe (Vousdoukas et al., 2017).

Figures for the Mediterranean basin are presented here (Figs. 12-15), while individual island maps can be found in the Annex. Figures for the Atlantic Islands were not included, due to the overall lack of confidence in the results currently obtainable, which does not recommend insistence on misinterpretable analyses.

Fig. 11 – Reference period: 20% of Wave heights for return times equal to 20, 10 and 5 years (from top to bottom). Top left: CMCC; top right: CNRM; bottom left: GUF; bottom right: LMD.

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Fig. 12 -RCP4.5 near future: 20% of Wave heights for return times equal to 20, 10 an 5 years (from top to bottom). Top left: CMCC; top right: CNRM; bottom left: GUF; bottom right: LMD.

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Fig. 13 – RCP4.5 far future: 20% of Wave heights for return times equal to 20, 10 and 5 years (from top to bottom). Top left: CMCC; top right: CNRM; bottom left: GUF; bottom right: LMD.

Fig. 14 – RCP8.5 near future: 20% of Wave heights for return times equal to 20, 10 an 5 years (from top to bottom). Top left: CMCC; top right: CNRM; bottom left: GUF; bottom right: LMD

Fig. 15 – RCP8.5 far future: 20% of Wave heights for return times equal to 20, 10 an 5 years (from top to bottom). Top left: CMCC; top right: CNRM; bottom left: GUF; bottom right: LMD

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Wave run-up

As already discussed in the previous section, total wave run-up is composed of wave setup and swash run-up. Accurate prediction of total wave run-up is crucial for coastal management, as it drives large morphologic changes induced by extreme storms, controlling the upper limit of beach erosion. The limit of wave run-up is also a key parameter in the classification of the morphologic impacts induced by storms, according to the storm-impact scale proposed by Sallenger (2000), who defines four levels by comparing the highest water elevation to a representative elevation of the barrier island (e.g., the top of the dune ridge). Among the various available empirical formulas that estimate wave run-up (Dodet et al., 2019), the results presented in this Report rely on that proposed by Roberts et al., 2010, which focuses on the morphologic response of the beach profile rather than on the hydrodynamics of wave run-up, with the explicit aim of providing a relation between the limit of wave run-up and the resulting beach change. Their tank experiments showed that the vertical extent of wave run-up above mean water level on a non-scarped beach is approximately equal to the offshore significant height of the breaking wave, and provided a very simple formula for predicting the total wave run-up, that is $R = 1.0 \cdot H$, which was then justified based on the ballistic theory of swash motion. A main advantage of their approximation is that it does not include beach slope, which is difficult to measure and is itself dependent on wave properties. They even found that including the slope-dependent surf-similarity parameter decreased the accuracy of the estimated wave run-up with respect to the measured values. However, their approximation is no longer valid for steep slopes, either already present or created by the incident wave dynamics during the storm, which substantially limit the up-rush of swash motion and induce wave reflection.

As for the wave setup figures, figures for the entire Mediterranean basin are presented here, while individual island maps are included in the Annex, also for the Atlantic Islands, as they were thought to give some hints on a worst-case evaluation, despite the need for further investigation. Additional label-bars allow accounting for the effects of the expected sea level rise under future climate scenarios. Patterns do not change between figures for the setup and the run-up, only the interpretation of the colors. Separate figures were produced in order not to overload the graphics with excessive information and to allow easier reference.

Fig. 16 – Reference period: Wave heights for return times equal to 20, 10 and 5 years (from top to bottom). Top left: CMCC; top right: CNRM; bottom left: GUF; bottom right: LMD.

Fig. 17 – RCP4.5 near future: Wave heights for return times equal to 20, 10 and 5 years (from top to bottom). Top left: CMCC; top right: CNRM; bottom left: GUF; bottom right: LMD.

Fig. 18 – RCP4.5 far future: Wave heights for return times equal to 20, 10 and 5 years (from top to bottom). Top left: CMCC; top right: CNRM; bottom left: GUF; bottom right: LMD.

Fig. 19 – RCP8.5 near future: Wave heights for return times equal to 20, 10 and 5 years (from top to bottom). Top left: CMCC; top right: CNRM; bottom left: GUF; bottom right: LMD.

Fig. 20 – RCP8.5 far future: Wave heights for return times equal to 20, 10 and 5 years (from top to bottom). Top left: CMCC; top right: CNRM; bottom left: GUF; bottom right: LMD

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Shoreline retreat in the Mediterranean basin

An alternative way of looking at future ESL-induced hazards is to consider the impacts of wave motion and surge onto a shoreline altered by the projected sea level rise. For the Mediterranean basin, we attempted a first estimate of the shoreline retreat at the regional scale by using the database of near-shore slopes developed by Athanasiou et al., 2019 (<https://doi.org/10.4121/uuid:a8297dcd-c34e-4e6d-bf66-9fb8913d983d> - spatial resolution: about 1 km along the global OpenStreetMap (OSM) coastline), and by applying the conservative rule (Bruun, 1962). This approach follows the steps of Thiéblemont et al., 2019, who further proceeded to interpolate the slope data on the sandy coastal segments provided by the EUROSION database (<https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/data/geomorphology-geology-erosion-trends-and-coastal-defence-works>) and estimated beach-area losses.

The results presented below (for mean and high end SLR scenarios and targeting the mid-century time horizon) only constitute an intermediate step towards the computation of the coastal vulnerability indexes that will be included in D4.5. They are, as could be expected, consistent with the findings of Thiéblemont et al., 2019, but also in reasonable agreement with projections obtained for the Balearic island by using a more rigorous approach (D4.4d).

Fig. 21 – RCP4.5 near future: estimated shoreline retreat due to the mean projected sea level rise for the Western (top) and Eastern (bottom) Mediterranean basin

Fig.22 – RCP4.5 near future: estimated shoreline retreat due to the high-end projected sea level rise for the Western (top) and Eastern (bottom) Mediterranean basin

Fig. 23 – RCP8.5 near future: estimated shoreline retreat due to the mean projected sea level rise for the Western (top) and Eastern (bottom) Mediterranean basin

Fig. 24 – RCP8.5 near future: estimated shoreline retreat due to the high-end projected sea level rise for the Western (top) and Eastern (bottom) Mediterranean basin

Fig. 25 – RCP4.5 near future: estimated shoreline retreat in the Balearic Islands due to the mean (top) and high-end (bottom) projected sea level rise

Fig. 26 – RCP8.5 near future: estimated shoreline retreat in the Balearic Islands due to the mean (top) and high-end (bottom) projected sea level rise

3. Conclusions

Results for the components of ESL-induced hazard were presented for the areas of interest of the SOCLIMPACT project, based on currently available model data. Data gaps were highlighted, especially for the Atlantic islands, for which global model simulations only provide too coarse and not fully reliable data, and the feasibility of high-resolution nested wave simulations is impaired by the lack of a representative set of spectral boundary conditions, not allowing the construction of an ensemble of sufficient size. Empirical formulas for the derivation of relevant cascading effects, mainly attributable to sea level rise, were discussed and applied to the data, and individual island maps presented in the Annex to this Report. A first evaluation of shoreline retreat was attempted for the Mediterranean islands, by combining the mid-century mean and high-end SLR projections and GIS-based data of near-shore slopes along the European coast. Analyses are on-going to further synthesize results into a climate-change dependent Coastal Vulnerability Index for the Mediterranean Islands, in order to integrate information from a multi-dimensional set of physical, geological, and, when feasible, socio-economic variables. Albeit such large-scale analyses cannot serve as the basis for local intervention, which demands ad-hoc monitoring and planning, they can effectively contribute to increasing social awareness as to climate-change-related hazards for insular communities, and help recognize the potential economic disadvantage faced by islands and highlight the most urgent priorities.

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**Work Package 4:
Modelling climate shocks and biophysical impacts**

**Annex to Deliverable 4.4b
Report on storm surge levels for different scenarios and different time horizon:
island projections**

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1. Introduction

For each of the islands selected in the SOCLIMPACT Project, the analyses described in D4.4b have been applied to derive a zero-order estimate of the local hazard originating from the combined action of Sea Level Rise (SLR) and wave motion. Starting from the need to support policy-making efforts in an effective and timely manner, this approach relies on very simple assumptions, which, having been proved applicable in a broad range of cases, cannot anyway substitute more thorough assessments that take into account the full complexity of the processes that govern coastal dynamics. Despite this limitation, however, such an approach can provide a first guidance in adaptation planning, by highlighting critical vulnerabilities and indicating when and where specific monitoring and additional modelling efforts are necessary or advisable, thus allowing a more effective allocation of resources. In particular, the presented results might prove useful in cases of high-risk aversion, for which the uncertainty tolerance is low and robust decision-making is required. To this purpose, the combined hazards were computed also for plausible—although unlikely - high-end SLR scenarios (i.e. the upper limit of the model ensemble spread), and for extreme wave heights corresponding to the longest reference return times compatible with the time-slices considered in this study (i.e. 10 and 20 years). Albeit such return times are too short to support the design of “hard” adaptation measures, whose life span is expected to be several decades long in order to guarantee cost-effectiveness, they could nevertheless be taken as reference to guarantee the return-on-investment of “soft” measures or of mid-term exploitation of coastal infrastructures (e.g. beach resorts). It must be always kept in mind, however, that the probability of having an event exceeding the N-year return level during the N-year time window is greater than that of its complement (see Table 2 of D4.4b), and that the return level does not represent a “no-risk” safety level. Moreover, it must be stressed that the presented results do not take into account the whole range of uncertainties of sea-level projections, as the quantification of the contributions from continental ice-sheet melting and the effects of the regional ocean dynamics and circulation changes is still a matter of debate. This is particularly true for semi-enclosed basins such as the Baltic and the Mediterranean Sea. The analysis for the Atlantic islands is also limited by the poor resolution of the wind field used to force the wave model, as well by the reduced ability of global models to correctly represent the dynamics across the equatorial and tropical belts, and the number, intensity and trajectories of tropical and extra-tropical cyclones (also related to spatial resolution). Refer to D4.4b for detailed information on methods and figures.

2. Mediterranean islands

Balearic Islands

Sea level Rise

Fig. 1 – Projected **Sea Level Rise** with respect to reference period: **RCP4.5 near future** (top left), **RCP4.5 far future** (top right), **RCP8.5 near future** (bottom left), **RCP8.5 far future** (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: high-end, mean and low-end

Wave Setup

Fig. 2 – Projected **Wave Setup** return levels - **Reference period**: CMCC (top left), CNRM (top right), GUF (bottom left), LMD (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 3 – Projected **Wave Setup** return levels – **RCP4.5 near future**: CMCC (top left), CNRM (top right), GUF (bottom left), LMD (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 4 – Projected **Wave Setup** return levels – **RCP4.5 far future**: CMCC (top left), CNRM (top right), GUF (bottom left), LMD (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 5 – Projected **Wave Setup** return levels – **RCP8.5 near future**: CMCC (top left), CNRM (top right), GUF (bottom left), LMD (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 6 – Projected **Wave Setup** return levels – **RCP8.5 far future**: CMCC (top left), CNRM (top right), GUF (bottom left), LMD (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Wave Run-up

Fig. 7 – Projected **Wave Run-up** return levels - **Reference period**: CMCC (top left), CNRM (top right), GUF (bottom left), LMD (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 8 – Projected **Wave Run-up** return levels – **RCP4.5 near future**: CMCC (top left), CNRM (top right), GUF (bottom left), LMD (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 9 – Projected **Wave Run-up** return levels – **RCP4.5 far future**: CMCC (top left), CNRM (top right), GUF (bottom left), LMD (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 10 – Projected **Wave Run-up** return levels – **RCP8.5 near future**: CMCC (top left), CNRM (top right), GUF (bottom left), LMD (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 11 – Projected **Wave Run-up** return levels – **RCP8.5 far future**: CMCC (top left), CNRM (top right), GUF (bottom left), LMD (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Corsica

Sea Level Rise

Fig. 12 – Projected Sea Level Rise with respect to reference period. From left to right: **RCP4.5 near future, RCP4.5 far future, RCP8.5 near future, RCP8.5 far future**. In each panel, from top to bottom: high-end, mean and low-end projection.

Wave Setup

Fig. 13 – Projected **Wave Setup** return levels - **Reference period**. From left to right: CMCC, CNRM, GUF, LMD. In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 14 – Projected **Wave Setup** return levels – **RCP4.5 near future**. From left to right: CMCC, CNRM, GUF, LMD. In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 15 – Projected **Wave Setup** return levels – **RCP4.5 far future**. From left to right: CMCC, CNRM, GUF, LMD. In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 16 – Projected **Wave Setup** return levels – **RCP8.5 near future**. From left to right: CMCC, CNRM, GUF, LMD. In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 17 – Projected **Wave Setup** return levels – **RCP8.5 far future**. From left to right: CMCC, CNRM, GUF, LMD. In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Wave Run-up

Fig. 18 – Projected **Wave Run-up** return levels - **Reference period**. From left to right: CMCC, CNRM, GUF, LMD. In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 19 – Projected **Wave Run-up** return levels – RCP4.5 near future. From left to right: CMCC, CNRM, GUF, LMD. In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 20 – Projected **Wave Run-up** return levels – **RCP4.5 far future**. From left to right: CMCC, CNRM, GUF, LMD. In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 21 – Projected **Wave Run-up** return levels – **RCP8.5 near future**. From left to right: CMCC, CNRM, GUF, LMD. In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 22 – Projected **Wave Run-up** return levels – **RCP8.5 far future**. From left to right: CMCC, CNRM, GUF, LMD. In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Crete

Sea Level Rise

Fig. 23 – Projected **Sea Level Rise** with respect to reference period: **RCP4.5 near future** (top left), **RCP4.5 far future** (top right), **RCP8.5 near future** (bottom left), **RCP8.5 far future** (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: high-end, mean and low-end projection.

Wave Setup

Fig. 24 – Projected **Wave Setup** return levels - **Reference period**: CMCC (top left), CNRM (top right), GUF (bottom left), LMD (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 25 – Projected **Wave Setup** return levels – **RCP4.5 near future**: CMCC (top left), CNRM (top right), GUF (bottom left), LMD (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 26 – Projected **Wave Setup** return levels – **RCP4.5 far future**: CMCC (top left), CNRM (top right), GUF (bottom left), LMD (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 27 – Projected **Wave Setup** return levels – **RCP8.5 near future**: CMCC (top left), CNRM (top right), GUF (bottom left), LMD (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 28- Projected **Wave Setup** return levels – **RCP8.5 far future**: CMCC (top left), CNRM (top right), GUF (bottom left), LMD (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Wave Run-up

Fig. 29– Projected Wave Run-up return levels – **Reference period:** CMCC (top left), CNRM (top right), GUF (bottom left), LMD (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 30– Projected **Wave Run-up** return levels – RCP4.5 near future: CMCC (top left), CNRM (top right), GUF (bottom left), LMD (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 31 – Projected **Wave Run-up** return levels – **RCP4.5 far future**: CMCC (top left), CNRM (top right), GUF (bottom left), LMD (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 32 – Projected **Wave Run-up** return levels – **RCP8.5 near future**: CMCC (top left), CNRM (top right), GUF (bottom left), LMD (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 33 – Projected **Wave Run-up** return levels – **RCP8.5 far future**: CMCC (top left), CNRM (top right), GUF (bottom left), LMD (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Cyprus

Sea Level Rise

Fig. 34 – Projected **Sea Level Rise** with respect to reference period: **RCP4.5 near future** (top left), **RCP4.5 far future** (top right), **RCP8.5 near future** (bottom left), **RCP8.5 far future** (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: high-end, mean and low-end projection.

Wave Setup

Fig. 35 – Projected **Wave Setup** return levels - **Reference period**: CMCC (top left), CNRM (top right), GUF (bottom left), LMD (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 36 – Projected **Wave Setup** return levels – **RCP4.5 near future**: CMCC (top left), CNRM (top right), GUF (bottom left), LMD (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 37 – Projected **Wave Setup** return levels – **RCP4.5 far future**: CMCC (top left), CNRM (top right), GUF (bottom left), LMD (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 38 – Projected **Wave Setup** return levels – **RCP8.5 near future**: CMCC (top left), CNRM (top right), GUF (bottom left), LMD (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Wave Run-up

Fig. 40 – Projected **Wave Run-up** return levels - **Reference period**: CMCC (top left), CNRM (top right), GUF (bottom left), LMD (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 41 – Projected **Wave Run-up** return levels – **RCP4.5 near future**: CMCC (top left), CNRM (top right), GUF (bottom left), LMD (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 42 – Projected **Wave Run-up** return levels – **RCP4.5 far future**: CMCC (top left), CNRM (top right), GUF (bottom left), LMD (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 43– Projected **Wave Run-up** return levels – **RCP8.5 near future**: CMCC (top left), CNRM (top right), GUF (bottom left), LMD (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 44 – Projected **Wave Run-up** return levels – **RCP8.5 far future**: CMCC (top left), CNRM (top right), GUF (bottom left), LMD (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Malta

Sea Level Rise

Fig. 45 – Projected **Sea Level Rise** with respect to reference period: **RCP4.5 near future** (top left), **RCP4.5 far future** (top right), **RCP8.5 near future** (bottom left), **RCP8.5 far future** (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: high-end, mean and low-end projection.

Wave Setup

Fig. 46 – Projected **Wave Setup** return levels - **Reference period**: CMCC (top left), CNRM (top right), GUF (bottom left), LMD (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 47 – Projected **Wave Setup** return levels – **RCP4.5 near future**: CMCC (top left), CNRM (top right), GUF (bottom left), LMD (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 48 – Projected **Wave Setup** return levels – **RCP4.5 far future**: CMCC (top left), CNRM (top right), GUF (bottom left), LMD (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 49– Projected **Wave Setup** return levels – **RCP8.5 near future**: CMCC (top left), CNRM (top right), GUF (bottom left), LMD (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 50– Projected **Wave Setup** return levels – **RCP8.5 far future**: CMCC (top left), CNRM (top right), GUF (bottom left), LMD (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Wave Run-up

Fig. 51 – Projected **Wave Run-up** return levels - **Reference period**: CMCC (top left), CNRM (top right), GUF (bottom left), LMD (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 52 – Projected **Wave Run-up** return levels – **RCP45 near future**: CMCC (top left), CNRM (top right), GUF (bottom left), LMD (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 53 – Projected **Wave Run-up** return levels – **RCP45 far future**: CMCC (top left), CNRM (top right), GUF (bottom left), LMD (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 54– Projected **Wave Run-up** return levels – RCP85 near future: CMCC (top left), CNRM (top right), GUF (bottom left), LMD (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 55 – Projected **Wave Run-up** return levels – **RCP85 far future**: CMCC (top left), CNRM (top right), GUF (bottom left), LMD (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Sardinia

Sea Level Rise

Fig. 56 – Projected **Sea Level Rise** with respect to reference period. From left to right: **RCP4.5 near future, RCP4.5 far future, RCP8.5 near future, RCP8.5 far future**. In each panel, from top to bottom: high-end, mean and low-end projection.

Wave Setup

Fig. 57 – Projected **Wave Setup** return levels - **Reference period**. From left to right: CMCC, CNRM, GUF, LMD. In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 58 – Projected **Wave Setup** return levels – **RCP4.5 near future**. From left to right: CMCC, CNRM, GUF, LMD. In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 59 – Projected **Wave Setup** return levels – **RCP4.5 far future**. From left to right: CMCC, CNRM, GUF, LMD. In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 60 – Projected **Wave Setup** return levels – **RCP8.5 near future**. From left to right: CMCC, CNRM, GUF, LMD. In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 61 – Projected **Wave Setup** return levels – **RCP8.5** for future. From left to right: CMCC, CNRM, GUF, LMD. In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Wave Run-up

Fig. 62 – Projected **Wave Run-up** return levels - **Reference period**. From left to right: CMCC, CNRM, GUF, LMD. In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 63 – Projected **Wave Run-up** return levels – **RCP45 near future**. From left to right: CMCC, CNRM, GUF, LMD. In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 64 – Projected **Wave Run-up** return levels – **RCP45** for future. From left to right: CMCC, CNRM, GUF, LMD. In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 65 – Projected **Wave Run-up** return levels – **RCP85 near future**. From left to right: CMCC, CNRM, GUF, LMD. In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 66 – Projected **Wave Run-up** return levels – **RCP85 far future**. From left to right: CMCC, CNRM, GUF, LMD. In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Sicily

Sea Level Rise

Fig. 67 – Projected **Sea Level Rise** with respect to reference period: **RCP4.5 near future** (top left), **RCP4.5 far future** (top right), **RCP8.5 near future** (bottom left), **RCP8.5 far future** (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: high-end, mean and low-end projection.

Wave Setup

Fig. 68 – Projected **Wave Setup** return levels - **Reference period**: CMCC (top left), CNRM (top right), GUF (bottom left), LMD (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 69 – Projected **Wave Setup** return levels – **RCP4.5 near future**: CMCC (top left), CNRM (top right), GUF (bottom left), LMD (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 70 – Projected **Wave Setup** return levels – **RCP4.5 far future**: CMCC (top left), CNRM (top right), GUF (bottom left), LMD (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 71 – Projected **Wave Setup** return levels – **RCP8.5 near future**: CMCC (top left), CNRM (top right), GUF (bottom left), LMD (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 72 – Projected **Wave Setup** return levels – RCP8.5 far future: CMCC (top left), CNRM (top right), GUF (bottom left), LMD (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Wave Run-up

Fig. 73 – Projected **Wave Run-up** return levels - **Reference period**: CMCC (top left), CNRM (top right), GUF (bottom left), LMD (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 74 – Projected **Wave Run-up** return levels – **RCP4.5** near future CMCC (top left), CNRM (top right), GUF (bottom left), LMD (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 75 – Projected **Wave Run-up** return levels – **RCP4.5 far future**: CMCC (top left), CNRM (top right), GUF (bottom left), LMD (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 76 – Projected **Wave Run-up** return levels – **RCP8.5 near future** CMCC (top left), CNRM (top right), GUF (bottom left), LMD (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

Fig. 77 – Projected **Wave Run-up** return levels – **RCP8.5 far future**: CMCC (top left), CNRM (top right), GUF (bottom left), LMD (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: 20-year return time, 10-year return time and 5-year return time.

3. Atlantic Islands

Azores

Sea Level Rise

Fig. 78 – Projected **Sea Level Rise** with respect to reference period: **RCP4.5 near future** (top left), **RCP4.5 far future** (top right), **RCP8.5 near future** (bottom left), **RCP8.5 far future** (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: high-end, mean and low-end projection.

Wave Run-up

Fig. 79 – Projected **Wave Run-up** return levels – Reference period: Hadley (left), ACC (right).

Fig. 80 – Projected **Wave Run-up** return levels – **RCP8.5 near future**: Hadley (left), ACC (right). The impact of Sea Level Rise on the 10-year (top) and the 5-year (bottom) return times is highlighted in the lower colour-bar.

Fig. 81 – Projected **Wave Run-up** return levels – **RCP8.5 far future**: Hadley (left), ACC (right). The impact of Sea Level Rise on the 10-year (top) and the 5-year (bottom) return times is highlighted in the lower colour-bar.

Canaries

Sea Level Rise

Fig. 82 – Projected **Sea Level Rise** with respect to reference period: **RCP4.5 near future** (top left), **RCP4.5 far future** (top right), **RCP8.5 near future** (bottom left), **RCP8.5 far future** (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: high-end, mean and low-end projection.

Wave Run-up

Fig. 83 – Projected **Wave Run-up** return levels – **Reference period:** Hadley (left), ACC (right).

Fig. 84 – Projected **Wave Run-up** return levels – **RCP8.5 near future**: Hadley (left), ACC (right). The impact of Sea Level Rise on the 10-year (top) and the 5-year (bottom) return times is highlighted in the lower colour-bar.

Fig. 85 – Projected **Wave Run-up** return levels – **RCP8.5 far future**: Hadley (left), ACC (right). The impact of Sea Level Rise on the 10-year (top) and the 5-year (bottom) return times is highlighted in the lower colour-bar.

Madeira

Sea Level Rise

Fig. 86 - Projected **Sea Level Rise** with respect to reference period: **RCP4.5 near future** (top left), **RCP4.5 far future** (top right), **RCP8.5 near future** (bottom left), **RCP8.5 far future** (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: high-end, mean and low-end projection.

Wave Run-up

Fig. 87 – Projected **Wave Run-up** return levels – **Reference period:** Hadley (left), ACC (right).

Fig. 88 – Projected **Wave Run-up** return levels – **RCP8.5 near future**: Hadley (left), ACC (right). The impact of Sea Level Rise on the 10-year (top) and the 5-year (bottom) return times is highlighted in the lower colour-bar.

Fig. 89 – Projected **Wave Run-up** return levels – **RCP8.5 far future**: Hadley (left), ACC (right). The impact of Sea Level Rise on the 10-year (top) and the 5-year (bottom) return times is highlighted in the lower colour-bar.

West Indies

Sea Level Rise

Fig. 90 – Projected **Sea Level Rise** with respect to reference period (shown for Puerto Rico): **RCP4.5 near future** (top left), **RCP4.5 far future** (top right), **RCP8.5 near future** (bottom left), **RCP8.5 far future** (bottom right). In each panel, from top to bottom: high-end, mean and low-end projection.

Wave Run-up

Fig. 91 – Projected **Wave Run-up** return levels – Reference period: Hadley (left), ACC (right).

Fig. 92 – Projected **Wave Run-up** return levels – **RCP8.5 near future**: Hadley (left), ACC (right). The impact of Sea Level Rise on the 10-year (top) and the 5-year (bottom) return times is highlighted in the lower colour-bar.

Fig. 93 – Projected **Wave Run-up** return levels – **RCP8.5 far future**: Hadley (left), ACC (right). The impact of Sea Level Rise on the 10-year (top) and the 5-year (bottom) return times is highlighted in the lower colour-bar.

4. Baltic Islands

Fehmarn (DE)

Sea Level Rise

Fig. 94 – Projected **Sea Level Rise** with respect to reference period: **RCP4.5 near future** (top left), **RCP4.5 far future** (top right), **RCP8.5 near future** (bottom left), **RCP8.5 far future** (bottom right). In each panel, from top to

Projections of extreme sea levels and shoreline retreat in the Baltic basin can be found in Vousdoukas and et al., 2017 (<http://data.jrc.ec.europa.eu/collection/LISCOAST>) and Thiéblemont et al., 2019 (see reference list in D4.4.b main document).

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